

Impulse Hits as a Source of Entropy Creation?

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Quantum mechanics for a free particle or even bound particle is based on the linear algebraic idea of eigenfunctions. For example, for both a free particle and bound particle, one writes a wavefunction which is an eigenfunction of the Hamiltonian ($p^2/2m + V(x)$ in the nonrelativistic case). Quantum mechanics goes a step further, however, and expresses p as $-i \hbar d/dx$, so one has a second eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$, namely that of the translational operator d/dx . Density, however, is $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} = 1/L$ showing no p dependence.. $\exp(ipx)$, however, does contain explicit x dependence and so we argue there is x based probability and hence entropy associated with this eigenfunction. We also point out that the MERW approach also uses the notion of eigenfunction.

We suggest that the idea of a $-i\hbar d/dx$ eigenfunction is really associated with the notion of a kind of spatial probability and hence spatial entropy. Thus, the real question seems to be: Why should a precise p value be associated with entropy? Where does this entropy come from? Why is there no entropy associated with velocity instead?

We suggest that entropy is created through an impulse hit, which thus concerns p and not v , because there is an uncertainty in both Δt and Δx when an impulse occurs. In other words, one does not know precisely how an impulse occurs within Δt , Δx regions. This leads to the idea of uncertainty, probability and entropy. Thus, an impulse hit creates entropy linked to p . This entropy is linked to a spatial frequency (wavelength) and its measurement in space (two slit apparatus etc) generates more entropy. The value of p is encoded in the probability function $\exp(ipx)$ and is decoded through the operator d/dx due to spatial invariance, hence the notion of an eigenfunction. Given that an impulse hit often pours energy into a particle, the more energy, the sharper the wavelength \hbar/p and the more order (less entropy) present. The natural tendency, however, is for a particle, during an impulse hit with another particle with much less momentum, is to shed its momentum/energy, i.e. increase its entropy, which is qualitatively consistent with the second law of thermodynamics.

Eigenfunctions in Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics, unlike classical mechanics or even classical statistical mechanics, seems to be associated with eigenfunctions and linear algebra theory. At first one may simply suggest that nature is described by this mathematical theory. We suggest, however, that there is an underlying physical reason for the emergence of eigenfunctions in quantum theory.

One may note that for both a free particle and bound particle, one has eigenfunctions of the Hamiltonian operator:

$$H = p^2/2m + V(x) \text{ nonrelativistically } ((1))$$

((1)), however, is a classical scalar quantity unless one makes p an operator, i.e. $-i\hbar d/dx = p$ as is done in quantum mechanics. The operator nature of H (which leads to an eigenfunction) follows from the operator nature of p momentum. P , however, is a precise number and a scalar in

classical mechanics. Why does it become an operator with an associated eigenfunction in quantum mechanics?

We also note that the idea of eigenfunctions appears in MERW theory in which one considers a transition matrix and tries to find its principal eigenfunction.

The Notion of Entropy

The concept of a momentum eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$ suggests variation in space which means a lack of certainty in space. One has two dimensions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, when space is normally associated with one dimension x , in a one dimensional problem. There is uncertainty in the $\cos(px)$ one dimensional component. We suggest that this is due to dynamics, i.e. the particle has some uncertainty to be at x , but is moving and there is uncertainty in the change in x , hence the two dimensional $\exp(ipx)$. This, however, does not explain where the x uncertainty comes from in the first place.

We suggest that there must be an underlying physical reason for the uncertainty, hence entropy, associated with $\exp(ipx)$. At first one may argue that:

$$\text{Density} = \exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} = 1/L \quad \text{where } L \text{ is length } ((2))$$

This contains no information about either p or velocity v . In other words, each x point carries the same weight which is associated with constant velocity motion. The density is one dimensional and constant and one might argue, linked entirely to deterministic motion. $\exp(ipx)$, however, is two dimensional and cannot be linked to deterministic motion in x . It seems it must be probabilistic. Furthermore, it is physical as manifested by a two-slit interference experiment etc. Thus, p momentum, is encoded in a kind of two dimensional (dynamic) $\exp(ipx)$ probability. This still begs the question: where does this probability (and hence associated entropy) come from and why is it not linked to velocity instead of p if it is dynamic?

Impulse Hits as a Source of Entropy?

Classical mechanics is based on precisely known values at all x and t because dx and dt intervals shrink to zero. Nevertheless, even in classical mechanics, changes occur within dx , dt . For example, if there is a force $F(x)$, a particle with $v(x)$ in dx changes its value and has $v(x)+dv(x)$ in the next dx interval. Thus, something occurs within dx whether it shrinks to zero or not. There is some uncertainty in dx as one does not know precisely how $v(x)$ changes in dx . In other words, one does not know precisely how the force $F(x)$ changes the particle. By shrinking dx to zero, one tries to eliminate this uncertainty and so classical mechanics eliminates, so to speak, uncertainty regions dx (by shrinking them to zero) and gives the impression of a deterministic theory. We suggest, however, that if there is an uncertainty in the delivery of $F(x)$ within a dx and dt , then the notion of probability and entropy exists. In other words, an impulse hit, by nature, creates or changes entropy. An impulse hit is associated with momentum p and not velocity v and so we suggest that this uncertainty or entropy is p dependent. This entropy cannot disappear and so there should be a probability function $f(x,p)$ associated with a precisely known p . In one dimension, however, there is smooth x motion and so no entropy appears in a

one dimensional scenario. A particle, however, is dynamic. It is at roughly one point, but is also changing and so one may have uncertainty associated with each dimension (position, change) and yet still have a modulus of 1 indicating smooth motion. Thus, entropy is encoded due to uncertainty in position and change in position in a momentum dependent way.

As a first step, one should try to calculate this entropy. Consider a static particle existing in one dimensional x space. One may not know its position (first moment) or second moment (and all the rest). Given translational invariance, one is not really interested in the average position of a static particle, but its second moment is of interest. Thus, one could try to maximize Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint on xx average:

$$\text{Extremize } P(x) \ln(P(x)) + b \int x^2 P(x) \rightarrow P(x) = \exp(-xx b) \quad ((3))$$

This leads to the well-known Gaussian solution.

What should one do for a moving particle? Motion is directly linked to velocity, but force to p momentum. Nevertheless a momentum p guarantees motion. For a moving particle, the first moment, x average, is critical. We suggested that there is both uncertainty in x and its change. Thus, there should be an $P(x,p)$ and a $P\text{change}(x,p)$. This suggests a two dimensional probability which maps into a constant, i.e. smooth constant motion. This suggests:

$$\{P(x,p) + i P\text{change}(x,p)\}^* \{P(x,p) + i P\text{change}(x,p)\} = \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{or } P(x,p) = \cos(px) \text{ and } P\text{change}(x,p) = \sin(px) \quad ((5))$$

No calculation of entropy, however, has been given, yet if there is a probability there should be an associated Shannon's entropy linked to a constraint on the first moment. One may see that an extremization of entropy result which yields ((5)) is:

$$\text{Extremize } -P_1(x) \ln(P_1(x)) + ipx P_1(x) \rightarrow P_1(x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

Here $P_1(x,p)$ is a complex probability linked directly to the precise value of p . In other words, entropy encodes the value of p momentum in x space. This suggests that to unlock the value of p using spatial means, one requires a frequency in space (i.e. distance) linked to the wavelength created by the uncertainty in position and change in position. A two slit apparatus is one such example of a device which may decode p . An interaction with this two slit apparatus, however, leads to a further increase in entropy due to interference. One has:

$$W(r) = \exp(i p_1 \cdot r) + \exp(i p_2 \cdot r) \quad ((7))$$

P_1 and p_2 have a magnitude of p , so the intrinsic entropy of each is the same as that of $\exp(ipx)$, but interference leads to a new entropy due to the probability ((7)). This follows from the physical uncertainty of going through one slit or the other. In other words, in order to create a wavelength type of measure in space using a static object (two slit apparatus), one must have

two physically separated interaction points (each slit) and this leads to an OR situation in probability which creates a new entropy based on the intrinsic entropy of $\exp(ipx)$

The Concept of an Eigenfunction

We noted above that $\exp(ipx)$ represents a two dimensional dynamic impulse based probability which may be obtained using maximization of entropy subject to an unusual constraint $\int x p P(x)$. We also noted that one may decode the momentum p , by having a static spatial object, like a two slit apparatus, which has two interaction points separated by a wavelength \hbar/p . The question becomes: Where is the notion of an eigenfunction? Formal quantum theory starts with the a priori notion of an eigenfunction of p given by the operator $-i\hbar/dx$. We suggest that one start with the notion of intrinsic entropy created/changed by an impulse and obtain a periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ which encodes information about p . It is based on extremization of Shannon's entropy subject to an $\int x p P(x)$ constraint. One may see that one calculates the first moment x , in the constraint, which is linked with p . Thus, the translation of the particle, associated with the operator d/dx , should also be linked with p . We suggest that this is why the notion of eigenfunction appears. The constraint used in extremization of entropy is linked to an operator associated with one precise value, namely p momentum.. This is the form of an eigenvalue equation. Thus, one has:

$$-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is often taken as a starting point to developing quantum mechanics, but we suggest that it is a consequence of the maximization of a Shannon's entropy using a dynamic two dimensional probability subject to a constraint on the first moment associated with a precise value of p .

Second Law of Thermodynamics

The second law of thermodynamics suggests an intrinsic increase in entropy if energy/work is not pumped into a system. Thus, a particle with precise p has entropy, but this particle should naturally try to increase its entropy. This happens if a particle with p encounters particles with p^2 which is very low. The natural tendency is for p to impart momentum and energy, thus dropping to a lower p value and a larger entropy.

Conclusion

Quantum mechanics often assumes, a priori, an eigenfunction of a momentum operator $-i\hbar/dx$. In other words, it is assumed that a priori that there exists a theory based on linear algebra and eigenvalue equations. Furthermore, it is not completely clear why momentum should be represented by the operator $-i\hbar/dx$.

We suggest that there should be an underlying physical principle justifying this linear algebraic formalism.. We argue that in classical mechanics, there is uncertainty within dx and dt as to how exactly a force(x) renders an impulse.. Classical mechanics, however, shrinks dx and dt to zero so that this uncertainty disappears and one is left with a deterministic theory. The

theory, however, makes it clear that changes occur within dx and dt and so these intervals cannot really be zero.

We suggest that an impulse hit due to $F(x)$ must be associated with uncertainties in dx and dt . An impulse hit creates a p , and so each p should have uncertainty in space and in time, which may be treated independently. Thus, there should be some kind of $f(p,x)$ probability which implies a Shannon's entropy. A given particle with precise p has entropy and if it undergoes an impulse hit, this entropy changes. A high p implies more order and less entropy. The natural tendency of a particle is to shed momentum and energy, i.e. move to a state of higher entropy. The question then becomes: How does one calculate this entropy? A particle moving in one dimension has a constant probability distribution over x . If one creates a dynamic probability based on p , however, one may have uncertainty associated with position and change in position, i.e. a two dimensional probability with a constant modulus. Thus, the idea of a wavelength is linked with two dimensional position and change uncertainty. This encoded p may be decoded by a static physical device which mimics a wavelength by having two interaction points separated by \hbar/p . Such an interaction, however, gives rise to additional entropy because $\exp(ipx)$ may interact with either interaction point etc. Given that one has probability in x , one should have Shannon's entropy. In fact, one may derive $\exp(ipx)$ by extremizing Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint on the first moment x $P(x)$ with a Lagrange multiplier of ip which brings in the two dimensional nature and the exact p value. It is from $\exp(ipx)$ that one finds that d/dx decodes the p value, i.e. an eigenvalue equation emerges. Thus, we suggest an underlying entropic reason for the use of eigenvalue equations in quantum mechanics.